

THEORETICAL AND METHODOLOGICAL PRINCIPLES OF IMPRESSIONISM AND THEIR MANIFESTATION IN PLEIN AIR PAINTING

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Abstract: In this article, the concept of impressionism and plein air painting in visual arts and the development of imagination of students in plein air practice are discussed. The world of fine art is a vast and diverse field that encompasses many different techniques, styles and approaches. One practice that stands out as a breath of fresh air – quite literally – is the age-old tradition of plein air painting. In recent years, teachers have realized the importance of including plein air practice in the curriculum, because it not only improves artistic skills, but also expands the imagination of students.

Key words: fine art, impressionism, plein air painting, increasing imagination, techniques, styles, emotion, artistic style, real experiences.

Impressionism (French impression - impression) is a direction in art that prevailed in the late 19th and early 20th centuries. Representatives of Impressionism strived to depict the existing being in movement and change in a more natural way, to express their momentary impressions, and achieved liveness and truthfulness of the image. The naturalness of reality, its constant change in the unity of man and environment was expressed.

It first appeared in French painting in the 1860s. E. Manet, K. Monet, O. Renoir expressed their vivid impressions of life in the expression of random movements and extraordinary situations. In landscapes, portraits, multi-form compositions, the power and purity of the first impressions, unique features were depicted by the artists without paying attention to small details. For the first time, the Impressionists created vivid views of modern city life and reflected its uniqueness in the form of the city landscape and people in their works. Landscape masters such as K. Monet, E. Degas, K. Pissarro, A. Sisley created their works in the open air and brightly reflected the shine of sunlight, the rich complex of colorful colors of nature, the plein air is the daily tone of their works with sunlight. gave a rich, romantic mood.

The works of mature Impressionists are distinguished by their brightness and vitality. Characteristics of impressionism developed in neo-impressionism and

post-impressionism. J. Whistler in America, M. Lieberman, L. Corinth in Germany, K. A. Korovin, I. E. Grabar and others in Russia. contributed to the development of I.'s creativity. In the 1880s and 1910s, I. significantly influenced the work of many artists. This was manifested in mastering new aspects of existence, mastering plein air methods. The rules of I. were reflected in different degrees in sculpture. French sculptors O. Rodin, Italian M. Rosso, Russian P. P. Trubetsky, A. Golubkina and others. in their works, they expressed movement, changes in form during movement.

The work of impressionist artists was also reflected in the development of Uzbek painting. Uzbek artists L. Bure, O. Tatevosyan, P. Benkov, 3. Kovalevskaya, A. Mirsoa-tov and others. this influence is felt in his works.

We can also see impressionist influences in the works of Karakalpak artists K. Saipov, J. Izentaev, M. Kudaibergenov, J. Bekanov, B. Serekeev.

The core of plein air practice lies in direct observation. Students step out of the classroom and into a world where the subject is not a static image, but a living, breathing entity. The transition from working with still life settings or photographs to working with dynamic, unpredictable elements of nature develops a deep connection between the artist and the environment. By improving observational skills, students learn to pick up the play of light, subtleties of color, and nuances of form. This first experience allows them to gain a deeper understanding of the subject and encourages a deeper appreciation of the world around them. The act of observing and interpreting the natural world encourages students to think critically about their environment and develop a sense of curiosity and inquiry.

The studio can be a safe space for artistic experimentation, but it can also be limiting. Plein air practice encourages students to break free from studio conventions where a controlled environment can stifle creativity. Outdoors, they encounter unpredictable weather, changing light conditions, and unexpected elements that force them to adapt and improvise.

Adapting to external factors cultivates a sense of resilience and resourcefulness, important qualities for any artist. Students learn to embrace the imperfection and unpredictability of the real world, turning challenges into opportunities for creative growth. Plein air practice pushes them out of their comfort zones, encouraging a more dynamic and flexible approach to their art. Engaging with the natural environment through plein air practice not only enhances artistic skills, but also deepens the connection between art and the world. Nature becomes both subject and partner, inspiring students to explore

the intersection of culture and the environment. Whether painting landscapes, cityscapes, or cultural events, students learn to incorporate specific features of the environment into their artwork.

Plein air practice also plays a crucial role in the development of a student's personal artistic style. The immediacy of working outdoors encourages spontaneity and instinctive decision-making. Students learn to trust their intuition and develop a unique visual language that reflects their personal interpretation of the world. By experimenting with different techniques and approaches in different outdoor settings, students gain a better understanding of what resonates with them artistically. Whether it's capturing the energy of a busy urban space or the tranquility of a rural landscape, plein air practice allows students to explore and refine their strengths, ultimately contributing to the development of their individual artistic identity.

In addition to the creative and imaginative aspects, plein air practice serves as an excellent tool for improving technical skills. Students are required to work quickly and efficiently as changing conditions require a faster pace than the controlled environment of a studio. This rapid execution encourages students to prioritize important elements such as composition, color harmony, and brushwork.

The need to adjust to changing light conditions also sharpens students' understanding of value and shade as they observe subtle changes in the landscape throughout the day. Plein air practice becomes a dynamic classroom where technical skills are not only learned but also tested in realistic scenarios, facilitating a holistic approach to artistic development.

Plein air practice goes beyond the individual artist and creates a sense of community among those who are passionate about working outdoors. Painting plein air often includes group tours, workshops, or events where artists come together to create, share ideas, and learn from each other. This sense of camaraderie creates an environment conducive to artistic growth and provides valuable opportunities for collaboration.

As the importance of plein-air practice in the visual arts becomes increasingly clear, educators are finding innovative ways to incorporate this tradition into art education. By expanding the scope and depth of outdoor experiences, students are given more opportunities to explore different landscapes, cultures, and artistic techniques. Some strategies for improving plein air practice in art education include:

- While traditional plein air paintings often conjure images of bucolic landscapes, urban environments provide plenty of inspiration. Cityscapes, streetscapes, and cultural events provide a dynamic backdrop for artistic exploration. Teachers can arrange tours of city centers that encourage students to reflect on the busy streets, architectural wonders and vibrant energy of city life.

- In the age of digital technology, plein air practice can go beyond traditional paintings to include digital art forms. Equipped with tablets or digital sketching tools, students can capture outdoor scenes in a variety of styles. This integration of technology is not only compatible with contemporary artistic practice, but also opens up new avenues for creativity and expression.

- Outdoor practice can be a vehicle for cultural exploration, allowing students to connect with different communities and traditions. By organizing cultural events, festivals or trips to historical sites, teachers give students the opportunity to create art that reflects the richness of different cultures. This approach promotes a broader understanding of the world and encourages students to consider the cultural context in their artistic expression.

- Collaborative projects that bring together students from different disciplines, such as literature, history, or environmental studies, can enhance the plein air experience. By integrating different perspectives, students gain a broader understanding of the topics they describe. For example, collaborations between art and environmental science classes can result in artwork that highlights environmental issues or celebrates the beauty of nature.

- Longer plein air residencies allow students to immerse themselves in a specific location. Whether it's a beachside retreat, a mountain landscape, or a city center, extended stays allow students to observe and interpret their environment for extended periods of time. It invites a deeper connection with the work environment for a long time and encourages a more nuanced exploration of the subject.

- In addition to creating art for personal expression, students can contribute to their communities through outdoor projects. In partnership with local organizations, students can implement public art initiatives that beautify public spaces, convey important messages, or celebrate community identity.

The exchange of perspectives, techniques and experiences within this community contributes to a rich tapestry of artistic inspiration. Students not only learn from their teachers, but also gain insight from their peers, broaden their artistic horizons, and expand their imaginations. The collaborative nature

of plein air painting creates a positive feedback loop, where each artist's unique vision contributes to the group's collective creativity.

Incorporating outdoor practice into the visual arts curriculum is a powerful way to enrich the learning experience for students. Born from direct observation of the natural world, this age-old tradition not only enhances technical skill, but also expands the imagination of aspiring artists. Through painting outdoors, students learn to embrace challenges, break free from convention, and develop a deep connection with their environment and culture.

Inviting established plein air artists or local professionals to hold workshops and share their experiences can provide valuable insights for students. Exposure to the practices and perspectives of experienced artists enriches the educational experience, gives students a glimpse into the professional art world, and provides guidance for their artistic journey. Expanding the concept of plein air practice in art education includes creative thinking about environments, themes, and techniques. Educators can provide students with a holistic and enriching arts education by embracing diverse landscapes, cultures, and technologies. The goal is not only to teach the technical aspects of painting, but to foster a love of discovery, a deep connection with the world, and an abiding passion for artistic expression. As the boundaries of plein air practice continue to expand, so does its potential to shape the next generation of imaginative and innovative artists.

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